

**MOBILE WALLETS: IS IT A SUBSTITUTE FOR
CURRENCY NOTES - AN USER PERCEPTION
ANALYSIS IN BANGALORE RURAL DISTRICT - A
DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS.**

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ABSTRACT

Advancement in digital technology brought in many new applications in all sectors and digital fund management and transfer applications gained more attention among both banks and users. All banks have their own digital applications while a few are not. The mobile wallets helps to transfer money using QR code, mobile number, UPI or net banking without going to bank or ATMs except for withdrawing or depositing cash. This paper analyse why the mobile wallets are not exact substitute for cash. Though the digital money management applications gained momentum in their down loads after demonetization, the demand for cash increased. This trend itself explained the ineffectiveness of mobile wallets in substituting the utility of cash. The analysis was conducted in Bengaluru Rural district in Karnataka. The result of the research shows that the liquidity of cash is the top priority for low income people and they prefer cash to digital cash. Also, the traders prefer cash to avoid tax commitments. The use of mobile wallets needs advanced mobiles and it is one of the limiting factor.

Keywords : mobile wallets, liquidity of cash transfer

Introduction

The history of exchange started from 'Barter system' to the digital 'cashless' transactions. The growth in computer and information technology along with communication technologies has evolved digital transaction. Mobile wallets, debit cards and credit cards by bypassing currency transactions. The perception on transaction itself changed. This paper analyses the customer preference towards M wallets in routine life along with its risk and challenges.

A brief history of Monetary transactions

The barter system was the ancient model of value exchange though it had a dispute in determining how much one commodity to be exchanged against another. Uniqueness was preciousness had been corner stone in determining the values. Later, the precious metals became standard for transaction, leading to the introduction of coins. The coinage was controlled by the governments in its value, quality and quantity based on its demand (Cipolla, 1956). The circulation of currency was regulated by Reserve Bank of India based on demand of cash. The demonetization in India in 2016 with an objective to promote the digital transaction. Though plastic cards like debit and credit cards have been another tool for transaction, the easiness in scanning the QR codes or using mobile number attached to a bank account to transfer of any amount made it popular among even in small retailers, taxis, hotels everywhere. The user fee for mobile wallet seemed to be zero comparing to debit cards and credit cards though mobile wallets cannot be used for cash withdrawals from Automatic Teller Machines (ATMs).

Demonetization and Digital transaction The objective of demonetisation was to reduce informal cash transactions and to increase formal cash transactions through banking, or indirectly a mode of financial inclusion. Being Indian economy is rich in informal economic activities than formal, it is difficult to implement financial inclusion due to the size of informal economy and transactions and manage the bank accounts for lower income people and illiterate as well. This limited the penetration of use mobile wallets in rural areas.

Literacy and familiarity with smart phones as well as related technologies is important in using Mobile wallets and though the use of smart phones increased in rural population, they are limited to calling, chatting etc than using for digital transactions.

Theoretical background

The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT)

UTAUT model (**The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT)**) model explain how technology adaption is influenced by the demographic variables of population. The technology adaption is affected a set of perceptions like fear of risk of loss and security, Lack of knowledge and experience in using technology limits adaptability (SARFARAZ & Alzubi, 2017). The technology adaption has two levels, individual level and social level. Personal efficacy, intelligence, technical capability, learning skill, and attitude towards new technologies while the social technology adaptability is a system driven and focussed like introduction and use of ‘Automatic Teller machines’ of Banks. The Banks introduce ‘ATM’ so that routine withdrawals can be removed from employees to ‘Machine’ that manpower need reduced. So, all bank customers need to learn how to operate ATM transactions. Personal interest in learning new technologies. The UTAUT model integrates personal attributes with product and environment attributes. Performance of a technology means its suitability and effectiveness of it fulfilling its utility to the customers while satisfaction of the customers gives the effectiveness. In the case of Mobile wallets, the existing literatures shows a mixed response influenced by the three-level technology adaption, Mobile technology, specific application attributes and use of M wallets. Adaption of Smart phone technology is common in urban population and reaching to semi-urban and rural areas. Continuously changing technology complexity, system requirements for different applications and user friendliness may surface as a challenge for low income, aged and low-income users. The satisfaction level may be explained if the frequency of its use increases. Social influence in mobile wallet is its convenient use in doing transactions of small amounts without carrying cash or using plastic cards. During CoVID 19, the transaction using mobile wallets increased to reduce physical transactions. Wide popularity in retail shops, even in small vegetable and fish vendors started adopted it. This shows that the technology adaptability by the individuals is a complex mix of personal efficacy and social influence. Adaption of many technologies in society is influenced by the strict implementation of policies and strategies to adapt a technology. Demonetization and CoVID prevention strategies became social influences in increasing popularity of Mobile wallets.

Review of Literature - The use of Mobile wallets by an individual is emerged from a complex attitude towards the use of technology, initiated by the curiosity to use latest technologies or constrained by the fear of ‘wrong use of applications’ or ‘loss of money’. Another fear is the possibility for exposure of transaction details if the mobile is lost. But this fear perception is gradually overruled by the convenience in spending or receiving, bank update after every transaction, convenience of transaction without cash, easy inter-transferability of money in between accounts, easiness to transfer fund using mobile number etc.

The application user friendliness in terms of appearance, readability, visual effects, etc also important in choosing an M Wallet app (Singh, Srivastava, & Sinha, 2017).

Mobility, convenience and trust are the three factors that attract customers to M wallets and to use M wallets in routine life (Deepti Sharma, 2019).

The United Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) is an integration of eight dominant theories and models, namely: the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Motivational Model, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), a combined TBP/TAM, the Model of PC Utilization, Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). Theory of reasoned action and Theory of Planned action are the basis to response to stimulations from environment like advertisement while the same stimuli is mixed with need and behavioural control, it become planned behaviour. The technology may be accepted if the need and benefits are perceived by the user and develop an attitude to use the technology. Innovation Diffusion Theory explained the level of adaption of technology. The SCT defines human behaviour as a triadic, dynamic, and reciprocal interaction of personal factors, behaviour, and the environment (Williams, Rana, & Dwivedi, 2015).

Statement of Problem

The technology adaptability is influenced by the socio-economic factors and the financial inclusion in urban area is deep while the same in rural areas is shallow due the higher degree of informality in living and trades. The UTAUT of Mobile wallets in urban areas shows a higher degree of adaptability in routine life while a thin use of it in rural areas. This paper analyses the relation between financial inclusion and UTAUT in urban areas.

Research Methodology

The data was collected using a structured questionnaire whose validity and reliability were tested using test and re-test method. The respondents of this research are of different ages, income, education, and **occupation and the number of respondents were 393**. In this research, the scale used is 5 point scale to understand the variation more vividly. The data is analyzed at the descriptive level and inferred based using mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis.

Objectiv of research

To understand the technology adaption in Bangalore rural districts.

Data Analysis

Table 1 : Descriptive Analysis : Demographic factors and factors that motivates mobile wallet use